

MANIFESTATION OF SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS DURING ADOLESCENCE

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ABSTRACT

This article focuses on the mental characteristics of adolescence, the formation of their consciousness and worldview, the issues of working with them, taking into account their age and psychological characteristics, and developing the skills to solve problem situations.

ПРОЯВЛЕНИЕ СОЦИАЛЬНО-ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ОСОБЕННОСТЕЙ В ПОДРОСТКОВОМ ВОЗРАСТЕ

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ABSTRACT

В данной статье основное внимание уделяется психическим особенностям подросткового возраста, формированию их сознания и мировоззрения, вопросам работы с ними с учетом их возрастных и психологических особенностей, развитию навыков решения проблемных ситуаций.

Education of the perfect generation is one of the important strategic issues, taking into account the demographic features of our country, this is not only a theoretical, but also a practical task. In today's globalization conditions, fierce battles for the human mind and soul

continue with the help of various methods and means. These actions are aimed directly at young people, and they are aimed at forming negative attitudes towards our national traditions and values, as well as the politics being carried out in our country. This is done by forming the necessary ideas and giving directions with the help of certain mass media, public art and culture.

The result can be observed in the cases of expansion in the religious, cultural, social and spiritual spheres of the society. Such situations, in turn, have the following consequences, which are of a tragic nature:

- narrowing of the circle of social relations of young people;
- change of value content;
- young people living only for today and not thinking about the future;
- Deformation of the figure of "I";
- occurrence of psychological depression (internal instability, internal conflict, social fear, accentuation of negative character traits);
- seeking to find one's place in places other than family, work, study group.

The main and leading type of activity in early adolescence is choosing a profession. In addition, at this age, a shift in self-awareness is evident. During this period, the desire to understand one's own spiritual world, personal qualities, intelligence, abilities and possibilities increases and becomes active. A desire to control one's behavior, to understand one's feelings and inner experiences begins to emerge. They begin to have the opportunity to more accurately assess their achievements and shortcomings, appropriate and inappropriate actions. On the basis of self-awareness, the desire for self-education is born. In self-education, early adolescence tries to eliminate its existing defects and strives to form positive qualities in itself. In this activity, the most important individual-psychological characteristics and character traits of a teenager are formed.

Character and imagination are extremely strong and permanent features, and its feelings in each person are clearly formed in connection with the development of social relations in historical conditions. From this point of view, people living in each historical period have behavioral characteristics related to the interests of the social system of the same period.

Usually, each person's personality traits and ideas related to them are very different, and these are integrally related to his will and moral qualities. These qualities include willpower, independence, determination, endurance, tenacity, and self-control. Moral-behavioral qualities of behavior include discipline, responsibility, kindness, sincerity, truthfulness, humanity, modesty, generosity, shyness, agreeableness, hard work.

The appearance and formation of a certain behavior in a person is reflected in the adaptation (orientation) to a certain value, and approximate assessment of them. It is possible to talk about orientation to value only when the subject projects a certain feeling in his mind. The formation of value orientation is activated by adaptation to needs and activities. Attention is paid to the behavior of people who are considered spiritual. For the same reason, the essence of spirituality is fully reflected in actions.

The force driving the psychic development of the early adolescent consists of the conflict between the level of demands of public organizations, school community, family, neighborhood

and the educational process and the level of mental maturity he has achieved, and these contradictions are eliminated by the rapid growth of his behavioral imagination.

The most intensive level of imagination formation corresponds to early adolescence. A system of knowledge about existence is formed in it, and there are clear ideas about events and objects of vital importance. In this system, there are very important elements for the person, and other perceptions of the person are aligned around these important elements. This level is characterized by the objectivity of imaginations, and they have a social nature in terms of their formation. In the same sense, attitudinal perceptions are highly formed social perceptions.

Behavioral ideas are a system of such ideas of a person, by means of which a person understands the concept of "spirituality" and all surrounding events and objects and has formed a certain attitude towards them. Since they are social, they include almost all spheres of "spirituality": connecting oneself with the fate of the Motherland, being proud of the history of the Motherland, science, religion, religious and national values, traditions, and ideas about the masterpieces of behavior created by mankind.

One of the most important advantages of a person is his knowledge of the external environment, his ability to adapt to it in different situations, and to develop adequate acceptable norms of behavior. Because a person should know and appreciate the social and cultural achievements of the society, and be able to enjoy them spiritually and mentally. This gives him the opportunity to correctly perceive and understand his time, makes the world of personal imagination flexible and rich. Logically based on this, we believe that attitudes are important because they play the role of a guiding and adjusting criterion for the behavior and behavior of a person in specific situations and in relation to the values in society.

Behavioral representations are a branch of social representations that are not fixed cognitive objects, but are constantly evolving, moving, and evolving. Its initial stage is the stage of perception, in which the information reflected directly in the mind is received, they are sorted in terms of awareness and necessity for the person. After that, the second stage - the stage of associative connections takes place, that is, new messages in the mind are compared with old ones, and associative and behavioral connections are taught. The common feature of the above second stage is generalization. The next stages are more related to the field of thinking and concepts, in which each information or message is differentially separated from the point of view of importance for the individual, and on this basis determines the direction of the individual's behavior in the form of certain conventions.

It should be said about the redevelopment of social imaginations that, in our opinion, the method of return plays an important role in this process. But what is being perceived over and over again has to be both emotionally and intellectually important to that listener. Feedback that has acquired certain personal meaning and content can lead to the strengthening of perceptions at the level of beliefs. At this point, it should be taken into account that if the information reaching a person's perception corresponds to his previous subjective perceptions, it is correctly recognized as objectively real and takes a place in the system of perceptions. may not be accepted as.

The social "dimensions" of a person are formed as a result of such criteria as the environment in which a person was brought up, the cultural processes he participates in, and communication. The social roles performed by a person in different groups (family, team, peer

group), as well as the subjective "I" about oneself formed as a result of certain impressions and influences, and the external "I" manifested as a result of the behavior expected of the person by others as important social components. classified.

A person is usually understood socially, not biologically. Because not all human beings are individuals. According to some scientists, all aspects in a person have a biological basis, and this basis is primary. That is, all human characteristics are innate. For example, character or abilities, like eye or hair color, are present from birth. Others believe that the human psyche is formed in certain relationships with other people, in the environment. Under the influence of these relations, a person's personality is formed, a person learns the values, manners, and customs of that society and environment.

Accessibility to communication, verbal and non-verbal reactions, behavior is slow. Most of the people of excitable type were "disobedient" in childhood, their behavior did not meet the requirements. He has never been disappointed in his studies since elementary school. Under constant supervision, they did their homework and assignments reluctantly. All bad labels are attached to them. They felt bad when they were alone.

A high level of anxiety is a subjective indicator of an unsuccessful person. Such individuals have a hostile attitude towards the surrounding people and environment. Therefore, they cannot give a correct, adequate assessment of the situation, their mood often changes quickly under the influence of the affective state. Such people's destructive activities are caused by their conscious or unconscious desire to protect their way of life from perceived dangers and threats. It should be noted that these threats can be perceived as imaginary, false, but real danger. As a result of constant mental stress and affective state, these persons sometimes start to play the role of "fighters for the truth" in defense of their rights. In this case, destructiveness is directed not at people, but at society. That is, even though these people do not actually create anything, and are unable to create anything, they protest and demand the elimination of all "injustices".

Thus, people who cannot satisfy their basic needs are prone to destructive activities, and as E. Fromm pointed out, they express their "I" by breaking and destroying. Destructiveness is an attempt to prove one's importance, first in one's own eyes, and then in the eyes of others, in a situation where it is extremely difficult to admit one's lack of weight, influence, and attention.

There are different views on the relationship between the individual and the society, in some of them, the individual is considered superior, and in others, the society is considered superior. In the explanation of the personality structure, a view is observed in terms of social roles, social position, and social sanctions. In managing a person's behavior, it is necessary to know his ideology, worldview, spirituality as well as his social institution. There are levels of self-esteem of a person in social relations: high, adequate, low, which in turn indicate different changes in the behavior of a person.

To sum up, psychologically, the motivations that lead a person to any (destructive or constructive) activity include his needs for security, respect, recognition, and finally to realize his creative potential and self-expression.

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